

ASSESSMENT OF FOOD HANDLING PRACTICES AMONG STREET FOOD VENDORS IN THE CENTRAL BUSINESS DISTRICT OF LUSAKA, ZAMBIA

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ABSTRACT

Background: Street food vending plays a critical role in urban livelihoods in Zambia, particularly within Lusaka's Central Business District (CBD), where rapid urbanization and unemployment have led to its expansion. However, poor food handling practices among street food vendors present a significant public health concern, contributing to the increased incidence of foodborne diseases such as diarrhea, cholera, and typhoid. This study aimed to assess the food handling practices among street food vendors operating in Lusaka's CBD, focusing on hygiene, sanitation, and food safety practices.

Methods: This was a cross-sectional study conducted among street food vendors in Lusaka's Central Business District between 21st February and 27th March, 2025. A convenience sampling method was used to recruit 369 vendors aged between 15 and 60 years who had been operating for at least four months. Data were collected using structured questionnaires, observation checklists, and interviews. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data using Microsoft Excel. Ethical clearance was obtained from the University of Zambia School of Medicine Research Ethics Committee (UNZASOMREC), and informed consent was sought from all participants to ensure compliance with ethical standards.

Results: Out of the 369 participants, 65.3% were female and 34.7% male. Most vendors (55.6%) were aged between 21 and 35 years, and 54.5% were married. A majority (64.2%) had no formal training in food handling and safety. The study revealed that 72.4% stored raw food at room temperature, and 52.8% did not separate raw from cooked food. Only 33.9% the street food vendors consistently washed their hands during food preparation, while 23.3% did not use soap and water. Although 78.3% wore clean attire and 85.9% covered their food, only 36.6% had access to handwashing facilities. Key challenges cited included lack of clean

water (77.2%), inadequate storage (72.6%), and high costs of protective clothing (70.7%). Notably, 92.1% believed food safety training would benefit them, and 94% expressed willingness to participate in future training programs.

Conclusion: This study found significant hygiene and food safety gaps among street food vendors in Lusaka's CBD. Despite positive attitudes, limited training and poor infrastructure hinder safe practices. To improve food safety and public health, targeted interventions such as hygiene education, improved facilities, and mobile training are urgently needed in Lusaka's informal food vending sector.

Keywords: Street Food Vendors, Food Handling Practices, Hygiene, Food Safety, Lusaka CBD, Zambia

INTRODUCTION

Food hygiene and safety are critical to public health. While street food vending plays a vital role in urban economies, it also poses significant food safety challenges due to its largely informal operations, making proper food handling essential.³⁰ In urban areas like Lusaka's Central Business District (CBD), street vending is widespread. However, limited research had previously been conducted on the food handling practices of vendors in this environment, hindering the development of targeted interventions for improving food safety.¹⁶

Inadequate food safety knowledge and poor hygiene practices are commonly observed among street food vendors, as noted by ¹ in Nigeria. Similar challenges were documented in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, where ²⁶ found that limited access to clean water and sanitation facilities exacerbated unhygienic conditions. Poor food handling practices can lead to contamination of food with harmful pathogens, including bacteria, viruses, and parasites, ultimately causing foodborne illnesses.

This study focused on assessing food handling practices among street food vendors operating within the dynamic and densely populated environment of Lusaka's Central Business District. As a major culinary hub, the CBD hosts a diverse range of street vendors who serve a large and varied consumer base. Ensuring food quality and safety in this setting is essential, given its significance as a primary food source for many urban residents.

Globally, the World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that one in ten individuals becomes ill from consuming contaminated food annually, resulting in approximately 420,000

deaths³⁶. In Zambia, foodborne illnesses remain a persistent concern, with pathogens such as *Salmonella* and *Escherichia coli* detected in commonly consumed street foods^{34, 12}.

Food safety risks can arise from natural elements, contamination, or degradation during production, storage, and distribution. Regulatory agencies establish permissible limits to protect consumers by defining the maximum acceptable levels of various hazards in food products.¹⁴ Food hazards are generally classified into microbiological, chemical, and physical categories. Microbiological hazards involve pathogens like bacteria and viruses, which can be introduced by food handlers or environmental factors.³² Chemical hazards include residues from veterinary drugs, pesticides, and heavy metals such as lead, often introduced during food production and processing.³⁸ Physical hazards refer to unintended objects such as glass shards, metal fragments, toothpicks, or hair, which may enter food at any stage and cause physical harm to consumers.³³

Assessing the food handling practices of street food vendors in the CBD of Lusaka was therefore necessary to identify critical gaps in hygiene and food safety. The findings of this study are intended to inform policy, support improved enforcement of food safety regulations, and contribute to broader public health strategies. Furthermore, the study adds to the existing body of knowledge on food safety, offering evidence-based insights applicable to similar urban informal food sectors both within Zambia and in comparable global contexts.

METHODOLOGY

Study Design

This was a cross-sectional descriptive study conducted in the Central Business District (CBD) of Lusaka, the capital of Zambia between 21st February and 27th March, 2025 to assess food handling practices among street food vendors using a structured questionnaire.

Target and Study Population

The study population included only street food vendors aged 15 to 60 years, operating in Lusaka's CBD for at least four months, and willing to participate in the study, while those who were not present during data collection, those below 15 or above 60 years of age, and those not willing to participate in the study were excluded.

Sample Size Determination

The sample size was determined using Cochran's formula with a 95% confidence level, 5% margin of error, and a 60% estimated prevalence from MOH (2018).

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \times P \times (1 - P)}{e^2}$$

Given that:

Prevalence (P) = 60% = 0.60

Confidence level = 95% (Z-Value for 95% Confidence level is 1.96)

Margin error (e) = 5% = 0.05

Where:

n = sample size

Z = Z-score (corresponding to the desired confidence level)

p = estimated proportion of the population that has a particular characteristic

e = margin of error

Substituting the given values into the formula;

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 0.60 \times (1 - 0.60)}{(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{0.921984}{0.0025}$$

$$n = 368.79$$

n = 369 Street Food Vendors

Sampling Technique

Convenience sampling was used to select street food vendors who were easily accessible within Lusaka's Central Business District during the data collection period, and each participant answered a structured questionnaire.

Data Collection Tool

Data collection in this study was carried out using a structured hard copy questionnaire, an observation checklist, and face-to-face interviews conducted with street food vendors in Lusaka's Central Business District.

Data Analysis

After data collection, the questionnaires and observation checklists were thoroughly checked for completeness and accuracy. The data was then manually entered into Microsoft Excel for analysis and summarized using tables, pie charts, and bar graphs to ensure clarity and ease of interpretation.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for this study was sought from the University Of Zambia School Of Medicine Undergraduate Research Ethics Committee (UNZASOMUREC). Participation was entirely voluntary, and participants were free to withdraw at any time without penalty. The researcher ensured anonymity and confidentiality, and informed consent was obtained after explaining the study's purpose, risks, and benefits to all participants.

RESULTS

Socio-demographic Data

A total of three hundred and sixty-nine participants were enrolled in this study, in which 241 (65.3%) were female and 128 (34.7%) were male. Most participants (55.55%) were aged between 21 and 35 years, followed by those aged 15 to 20 years (26.0%). A smaller proportion were aged 36 to 45 years (11.65%), while the least represented age group was 46 to 60 years (6.8%). Two hundred and one (54.5%) participants were married, one hundred and thirty-four (36.3%) were single and thirty-four (9.2%) were divorced. One hundred and sixty-three respondents had completed primary education, 72 did not have formal education, 79 attained secondary education, while only 55 attained tertiary education.

Furthermore, 46.9% had been operating for 1 to 5 years, followed by 27.6% who had been vending for 2 to 6 months, 16.8% for 7 to 12 months, and only 8.7% had been in business for

less than 2 months. Regarding the type of food sold, cooked meals were the most common (27.6%), followed closely by snacks (25.5%), beverages (23.6%), and fruits/vegetables (21.4%). A small proportion (1.9%) reported selling other types of food. (Table 2.0)

Food Handling Practices

Two hundred and thirty-seven (64.2%) had no formal training in food handling and safety, while only one hundred and thirty-two (35.8%) reported having received such training. Most vendors (72.4%) stored raw food at room temperature, 23.3% used refrigeration, and 4.3% used other methods. In terms of hand hygiene, 33.9% reported always washing hands while preparing food, 32.8% said often, 22.8% sometimes, and 10.5% never. Similarly, 76.7% claimed to wash their hands with soap and water before handling food, while 23.3% did not. When asked about food separation, 52.8% of vendors admitted they did not store raw and cooked food separately, raising concerns about cross-contamination risks. Only 47.2% reported adhering to this important safety practice. With regard to utensil cleaning, half of the vendors (50.4%) cleaned their cooking and serving utensils after every use, 26.0% cleaned them once a day, and 23.6% did so rarely. Lastly, for maintaining vending area cleanliness, the study revealed that 56.9% used regular sweeping, while 43.1% used disinfectants (Table 3.0).

Hygiene Practices

One hundred and twenty-three respondents (33.3%) indicated that they ‘sometimes’ wore clean and appropriate clothing while preparing food, 110 respondents (29.8%) reported ‘always’ wearing proper attire, 71 participants (19.2%), stated they ‘rarely’ did so, while 65 respondents (17.6%) admitted to ‘never’ wearing clean and appropriate clothing during food preparation (Figure 1.0).

Two hundred and eighty-nine respondents (78.3%) reported wearing clean and appropriate attire while vending food, whereas 80 (21.7%) admitted not doing so. Three hundred and seventeen (85.9%) vendors stated that they cover their food items to protect them from dust, while only fifty-two (14.1%) reported not doing so. However, when asked about access to handwashing facilities near their vending sites, only 36.6% of the respondents confirmed having access, while a substantial 63.4% reported not having any handwashing facility nearby (Table 4.0).

Food Safety Knowledge

Two hundred and four (55%) participants indicated that they were aware of foodborne illnesses and how they can be prevented, while 165 (45%) reported lacking such knowledge (Figure 2.0). Two hundred and seventy-two participants indicated that they acquired their knowledge through self-learning, while 75 reported learning through training programs. Only 22 (6%) respondents cited other sources like advice from inspectors and traditional knowledge (Figure 3.0).

It was also observed that the most frequently reported practice of food safety for consumption was cooking food thoroughly, selected by 325 respondents (88.1%), followed by using clean utensils (312 respondents; 84.6%) and using clean water (301 respondents; 81.6%). Additionally, 283 vendors (76.7%) reported keeping the vending area clean, while 240 (65.0%) indicated that they regularly wash their hands during food preparation. A smaller proportion, 94 respondents (25.5%), selected other, which included measures such as avoiding expired ingredients and covering food (Figure 4.0).

Challenges

Two hundred and eighty-five respondents lacked clean water, 268 respondents lacked adequate storage facilities, 252 lacked knowledge on food safety and 218 had limited access to handwashing facilities. Additionally, 261 respondents (70.7%) reported that the high cost of protective clothing such as gloves, aprons, and head coverings limited their ability to maintain hygiene during food vending operations, while the remaining 32 respondents (8.7%) accounted for challenges such as harassment from authorities, lack of waste disposal facilities (Figure 5.0).

Vendors Perceptions and Attitudes

A significant majority 340 (92.1%) of respondents believed that more training on food safety would benefit them and their business, while only 7.9% (29) disagreed. Furthermore, an even greater proportion (94%) expressed willingness to participate in future studies or training sessions related to food safety, with just 6% unwilling to do so (Table 5.0).

Table 2.0: Sociodemographic Data

<i>Sociodemographic Data</i>	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Gender</i>		
<i>Female</i>	241	65.3%
<i>Male</i>	128	34.7%
<i>Age in years</i>		
<i>15 – 20</i>	96	26.0%
<i>21 – 35</i>	205	55.55%
<i>36 – 45</i>	43	11.65%
<i>46 – 60</i>	25	6.8%
<i>Marital Status</i>		
<i>Married</i>	201	54.5%
<i>Single</i>	134	36.3%
<i>Divorced</i>	34	9.2%
<i>Level of Education Attained</i>		
<i>Primary Education</i>	163	44.2%
<i>Secondary Education</i>	79	21.4%
<i>Tertiary Education</i>	55	14.9%
<i>No Formal Education</i>	72	19.5%
<i>Duration of Street Food Vending Experience</i>		
<i>< 2 Months</i>	32	8.7%
<i>2 – 6 Months</i>	102	27.6%
<i>7 – 12 Months</i>	62	16.8%
<i>1 – 5 Years</i>	173	46.9%
<i>Types of Food Sold</i>		
<i>Cooked Meals</i>	102	27.6%
<i>Snacks</i>	94	25.5%
<i>Beverages</i>	87	23.6%

<i>Fruits/Vegetables</i>	79	21.4%
<i>Other</i>	7	1.9%

Table 3.0: Food Handling Practices

Variable	Attribute	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Do you have any formal training in food handling and safety?</i>	- Yes	132	35.8%
	- No	237	64.2%
<i>How do you store raw food materials?</i>	- Refrigeration	86	23.3%
	- At room temperature	267	72.4%
	- Other	16	4.3%
<i>How often do you wash your hands while preparing food?</i>	- Always	125	33.9%
	- Often	121	32.8%
	- Sometimes	84	22.8%
	- Never	39	10.5%
<i>Do you wash your hands with soap and water before handling food items?</i>	- Yes	283	76.7%
	- No	86	23.3%
<i>Do you store raw and cooked food items separately to prevent cross-contamination?</i>	- Yes	174	47.2%
	- No	195	52.8%
<i>How often do you clean your cooking and serving utensils?</i>	- After every use	186	50.4%
	- Once a day	96	26.0%
	- Rarely	87	23.6%
<i>How do you ensure the cleanliness of your vending area?</i>	- Regular sweeping	210	56.9%
	- Using disinfectants	159	43.1%

Figure 1.0: Wearing Clean & Appropriate Clothing

Table 4.0: Hygiene Practices

Variable	Attribute	Frequency	Percentage
Do you wear clean and appropriate attire while vending food?	- Yes	289	78.3%
	- No	80	21.7%
Do you cover your food items to protect them from dust?	- Yes	317	85.9%
	- No	52	14.1%
Do you have access to a handwashing facility near your vending site?	- Yes	135	36.6%
	- No	234	63.4%

Figure 2.0: Foodborne illnesses and prevention

Figure 3.0: Knowledge about Food Safety

Figure 4.0: Safety of the Food sold for Consumption

Figure 5.0: Challenges faced in maintaining food safety and hygiene

Table 5.0: Perceptions and Attitudes

Variable	Attribute	Frequency	Percentage
Do you believe that more training on food safety would benefit you and your business?	- Yes	340	92.1%
	- No	29	7.9%
Are you willing to participate in future studies or training sessions related to food safety?	- Yes	347	94%
	- No	22	6%

DISCUSSION

This study examined food handling practices, hygiene behaviors, safety knowledge, and associated challenges among street food vendors in Lusaka's Central Business District. The findings revealed that the majority of vendors were female (65.3%), predominantly within the economically active age range of 21-35 years (55.55%), and had limited formal education, with 44.2% having only primary education and 19.5% having no formal education. Critically, 64.2% of vendors lacked formal training in food safety, and only 23.3% had access to refrigeration for food storage. While 55% of vendors demonstrated general awareness of foodborne illnesses, significant gaps were identified in key hygiene practices including inconsistent hand hygiene (10.5% never washed hands during preparation), inadequate food separation (52.8% did not separate raw and cooked foods), and limited access to handwashing facilities (63.4% had no access). Despite these challenges, vendors exhibited positive attitudes toward training, with 92.1% expressing desire for additional food safety education and 94% willing to participate in future training programs.

The study's primary strengths include its substantial sample size of 369 participants and its focus on a high-density urban vending area where food safety risks are most pronounced. The use of structured questionnaires enabled systematic data collection across multiple dimensions of food safety practices, while direct observations provided valuable contextual insights into vendor behaviors. The high response rate and vendor willingness to participate (94%) demonstrate good community engagement and suggest data reliability.

However, several limitations warrant acknowledgment. Financial constraints restricted the scope of fieldwork activities and may have limited follow-up opportunities with participants. The busy street environment during data collection potentially introduced response bias, as vendors may have modified their responses in the presence of customers or fellow vendors. The low educational attainment of many participants necessitated additional clarification during questionnaire administration, which may have affected response accuracy. Furthermore, the compressed two-week data collection period limited opportunities for deeper engagement and seasonal variation assessment. The study's cross-sectional design precludes causal inference, and the underrepresentation of mobile and evening vendors may limit generalizability to the entire street food vendor population.

The gender distribution observed in this study, with female predominance in street food vending, is consistent with findings from similar urban informal food sector studies across sub-Saharan Africa and other developing regions. This consistency strengthens the external validity of our demographic findings and reflects broader socioeconomic patterns where women utilize street vending as an accessible income-generating activity.

The low rates of formal food safety training (35.8%) align with studies conducted in comparable settings, where informal sector workers frequently lack access to structured education programs. Similarly, infrastructural deficits, particularly limited access to clean water (77.2% cited as a challenge) and refrigeration (only 23.3% with access), mirror findings from other studies in resource-limited urban environments. These consistencies suggest that the challenges identified are not unique to Lusaka but represent systemic issues affecting street food safety across similar contexts.

However, this study's finding that 85.9% of vendors covered their food items represents a relatively higher compliance rate compared to some studies in other African cities, potentially reflecting greater awareness in Lusaka's CBD or the influence of customer expectations in high-visibility vending locations. The strong willingness to participate in training (94%) also appears notably higher than reported in some comparable studies, suggesting a particularly receptive environment for intervention in this population.

A notable discrepancy exists between vendors' reported awareness of food safety measures and their actual implementation. While 88.1% reported cooking food thoroughly and 84.6% claimed to use clean utensils, only 65% consistently washed their hands during food

preparation, and 10.5% never did so. This gap between knowledge and practice suggests that awareness alone is insufficient to ensure behavioral compliance.

Additionally, while 78.3% reported wearing clean attire while vending, detailed observation revealed that only 29.8% "always" wore appropriate clothing during preparation, with 33.3% doing so only "sometimes." This discrepancy may reflect social desirability bias in self-reported data or genuine variability in practice depending on circumstances.

The predominant reliance on self-directed learning (74%) rather than formal training programs (20%) for food safety knowledge represents an important finding that may explain inconsistencies in practice. Self-acquired knowledge, while valuable, may lack the comprehensiveness and accuracy of structured training, leading to gaps in critical areas such as temperature control and cross-contamination prevention.

This study provides critical evidence that street food vendors in Lusaka's CBD operate under significant constraints that compromise their ability to maintain adequate food safety standards, despite generally positive attitudes and willingness to improve. The findings demonstrate that food safety challenges in the informal sector are multifactorial, stemming from infrastructural inadequacies, limited access to education, economic barriers, and regulatory gaps rather than vendor negligence or lack of concern.

The high prevalence of inadequate food storage practices and limited access to clean water and handwashing facilities indicates that vendors' capacity to implement safe food handling is constrained by environmental and structural factors beyond their individual control. The overwhelming willingness to participate in training programs (94%) suggests that vendors recognize the importance of food safety and are motivated to improve when given appropriate support.

These findings have important implications for public health policy in urban informal food systems. They suggest that interventions focusing solely on vendor education without addressing infrastructural and economic barriers will likely achieve limited success. Instead, comprehensive approaches combining training, infrastructure improvement, and economic support are necessary to meaningfully enhance food safety in street food environments.

Several important questions remain inadequately addressed and warrant further investigation. First, longitudinal studies are needed to assess whether improved training and infrastructure lead to sustained behavioral change and measurable reductions in foodborne illness incidence

among consumers. The causal relationship between specific interventions and health outcomes requires prospective evaluation.

Second, the study did not examine microbial contamination levels in street-vended foods, which would provide objective measures of food safety risk and help prioritize intervention areas. Future research should incorporate laboratory analysis to complement self-reported data on hygiene practices.

Third, the economic dimensions of food safety compliance require deeper exploration. Understanding the cost-benefit analysis from vendors' perspectives, including the economic impact of food safety investments on profitability and customer retention, would inform the design of economically viable intervention strategies.

Fourth, the role of regulatory enforcement and its effectiveness in the informal food sector remains unclear. Research examining the relationship between inspection frequency, regulatory approaches, and vendor compliance would inform more effective governance strategies.

Fifth, this study did not adequately capture the experiences of mobile and evening vendors, who may face different challenges and require tailored interventions. Targeted research on underrepresented vendor categories would enhance the comprehensiveness of food safety programming.

Finally, consumer perspectives, knowledge, and behaviors regarding street food consumption were not examined. Understanding demand-side factors, including consumer willingness to pay for improved food safety and their role in incentivizing vendor compliance, would provide a more complete picture of the street food safety ecosystem and inform demand-driven intervention approaches.

Limitations

This study had several methodological and practical limitations that should be considered when interpreting the findings. Financial constraints limited the scope of fieldwork, affecting the printing of materials for 369 participants and restricting transport and logistical capacity. Data collection in busy and noisy street environments may have influenced participant concentration and introduced response bias due to the presence of customers or nearby vendors. The limited formal education among many participants necessitated additional clarification during questionnaire administration, potentially affecting response accuracy.

Time constraints restricted fieldwork to approximately two weeks, limiting opportunities for deeper engagement or follow-up clarification. Finally, inconsistent vendor availability, particularly among mobile vendors, affected sampling consistency and may have led to underrepresentation of certain vendor categories, including mobile and evening vendors. These limitations should be addressed in future research through extended data collection periods, mixed-methods approaches, and targeted sampling strategies for underrepresented vendor groups.

CONCLUSION

This study found that the majority of street food vendors in Lusaka's Central Business District practiced basic hygiene measures such as covering food and wearing appropriate attire. However, significant gaps were observed in areas such as hand hygiene, access to clean water, food storage, and formal training on food safety.

While most vendors demonstrated awareness of key food safety principles, the lack of consistent infrastructure particularly access to handwashing facilities and refrigeration undermined their ability to fully adhere to recommended food handling practices. The study also found that a large proportion of vendors had not received any formal training in food safety, and many relied on self-learning or informal knowledge.

Despite these challenges, vendors expressed a strong willingness to improve their practices and participate in future training programs. This positive attitude highlights the potential for impactful interventions that could enhance food safety standards within the informal food sector.

These findings underscore the need for comprehensive strategies that address infrastructural, educational, and regulatory barriers to safe food vending. Strengthening training programs, improving access to sanitation facilities, and supporting vendors through policy and community-based efforts will be essential to reducing foodborne disease risks and promoting public health in Lusaka's CBD.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. In future, efforts should be made to provide structured food safety training programs targeting street food vendors, focusing on hygiene practices, cross-contamination prevention, and proper food storage techniques.
2. Ministry of Local Government and Rural Development should collaborate with Lusaka City Council and other public health stakeholders like Water Aid Zambia and

WASH to install handwashing stations, ensure a steady supply of clean water, and improve waste disposal facilities in areas where vendors operate.

3. Awareness campaigns should be intensified to educate vendors and consumers alike on the risks associated with poor food handling practices and the importance of personal and environmental hygiene.
4. Provide vendors with affordable or subsidized safety materials like aprons, gloves, hairnets, and food covers. This small support can make a big difference in improving hygiene standards.
5. Regular routine health inspections and supportive supervision should be strengthened by local authorities to ensure compliance with food safety guidelines while promoting a culture of continuous improvement.
6. Further research should be conducted to assess the effectiveness of food safety interventions and to explore behavioral, economic, and cultural factors influencing hygiene practices among street food vendors in urban settings.
7. Stakeholders such as the Ministry of Health and local NGOs should engage in community-based education initiatives that use local languages and culturally relevant materials to enhance understanding of food safety among vendors with low literacy levels.
8. Introduce mobile training and certification units that can travel within the CBD to register, educate, and certify street food vendors on safe food handling practices in a cost-effective and accessible manner as this will encourage higher participation rates.
9. Design policies that support formal recognition and regulation of street food vending, which would include licensing, access to designated vending areas, and regular public health education.

What is already known on this topic

1. The demographic profile of street food vendors in developing countries
2. Known contributors to foodborne disease risks in informal food sectors
3. Common systemic challenges faced by vendors in resource-limited settings

What this study adds

1. Specific quantitative evidence of food safety gap prevalence in Lusaka's CBD

2. The remarkably high willingness to participate in training programs (94%) - a novel and important finding
3. The identification of self-directed learning as a key factor explaining the knowledge-practice gap

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I extend my gratitude to God Almighty for His guidance throughout my studies. Special thanks to my supervisor, Dr. Meki, for her invaluable support and mentorship. I also appreciate the University of Zambia's School of Public Health for granting me the opportunity to conduct this research. Lastly, my heartfelt thanks to my family, classmates, and friends for their encouragement and unwavering support.

Competing interest

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Funding

The authors did not obtain any funds for the conduct of this study. Author's contributions All authors contributed to the conception and design; acquisition, analysis and interpretation of data; drafting and revising the article and final approval of the version to be published.

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